

Supplementary Figures:

Supplementary Figure S1: Individual scores for the scales of the inventory of eating disorders with significant reductions through metreleptin treatment. Contr., healthy control participant.

Supplementary Figure S2: Metreleptin-associated brain connectivity increase detected with functional MRI showing an increase of eigenvector centrality (EC) for patient no. 1 over 12 weeks of metreleptin treatment. Orthogonal brain sections show normalized EC values (color-coded) for all voxels within the region obtained by the statistical analysis (see Figure 3 A). L, left; R, right; x, y, z, coordinates in mm.